

Interactive Clustering through Deep Metric Learning: A Study on Loss Functions

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Abstract

Clustering is a widely used and powerful technique for analyzing and extracting information from large-scale data. When applied to web data, it can help organize and interpret large volumes of content with minimal manual effort. However, due to its non-deterministic nature, different clustering results can be equally valid, rendering the notion of the “correct” clustering dependent on the end-users’ goals. Interactive clustering addresses this issue by incorporating user feedback, thus allowing users to refine results based on their (domain-specific) knowledge. Users can adjust clustering algorithms and their parameters, or directly modify clusters either by splitting and merging them, or by enforcing pairwise constraints to data. While these traditional methods of interactive clustering have been widely studied, recent work has increasingly focused on leveraging deep metric learning to adapt the clustering outcomes according to user guidance. This work explores how *deep metric learning* enhances clustering by adjusting similarity representations of documents to align with user-driven modifications. Specifically, we examine a framework that combines topic modeling with interactive clustering, where topics describe each cluster’s focus and users can move topic terms between clusters according to their preferences. We evaluate and compare four (4) popular loss functions within this framework, simulating user interventions to assess how well each approach supports iterative refinements. Results across seven (7) benchmark datasets highlight the loss functions that most effectively capture user intent and, in turn, improve the adaptability and robustness of clustering in dynamic web contexts. Overall, this study underscores the crucial role of deep metric learning in interactive clustering, being the first to evaluate the effectiveness of recent loss functions in aligning learned textual representations with user-driven clustering modifications.

Keywords

Interactive clustering, Deep metric learning, Loss functions, User simulation

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1 Introduction

Clustering and topic modeling are fundamental methodologies for revealing hidden patterns in large, high volume datasets, particularly in web environments where information is diverse and unstructured. Clustering enables the grouping of similar documents to uncover latent structures, while topic modeling provides interpretable summaries of document collections in the form of topics. Together, they serve as powerful tools for exploring information-rich environments. Here, clustering alongside topic modeling is used to create an effective approach to study interactive clustering.

While clustering provides an overview of data distribution, its non-deterministic nature poses significant challenges: changes in algorithms, parameters, or initialization can produce multiple results that appear equally informative. This variability poses issues of trust and adaptability, as the “best” clustering often depends on the user’s goals and expertise. These challenges become even more critical as datasets grow more complex and dynamic. In today’s web environment in particular, where data are highly complex and rapidly evolving, and where generative AI accelerates the creation of vast amounts of content while introducing risks of misinformation, manipulation, and loss of trust [27], these issues are further amplified. A reliable and adaptive clustering method could help understanding and navigating such challenges by providing trustworthy and interpretable results.

Traditional clustering methods are inflexible in adapting to varying needs, as they typically require users to predefine parameters and select an algorithm without prior knowledge of how these choices will impact the final results. Interactive clustering addresses these limitations by integrating user feedback into the process, enabling users to refine results according to their (domain-specific) knowledge [2]. Traditional approaches include splitting and merging clusters [1, 3], adjusting clustering parameters [8, 11, 23], or enforcing pairwise constraints [19, 21, 39]. One particularly promising approach in interactive clustering is the dynamic modification of data representations to better fit user expectations through *metric learning*, as it incorporates user feedback directly into data representations and improves generalization to unseen data. At its core,

metric learning aims to learn a function that measures the similarity between data samples.

In this work, we investigate the impact of deep metric learning on interactive clustering. Although interactive clustering has shown promising results, recent deep metric learning techniques have not yet been explored in this context. Specifically, we examine the effect of various loss functions on optimizing cluster representations and evaluate interactive clustering by simulating user interactions. The main contributions of this study are:

- A framework for interactive document clustering that combines topic modeling with metric learning, enabling intuitive user interventions and adaptive similarity representations.
- The first comparative analysis of four (4) deep metric learning loss functions in the context of interactive clustering, highlighting strengths and limitations and addressing a gap in current research.
- Extensive evaluations on seven (7) benchmark datasets, where user behavior is simulated through entropy-driven adjustments, demonstrating how deep metric learning improves adaptability and robustness of clustering, while strengthening trust in web-based information systems.
- The full implementation code will be made publicly available (upon acceptance) to support reproducibility.

2 Related Work

Metric learning approaches. Interactive clustering focuses on integrating user feedback into the clustering process. Several studies have explored combining interactive clustering with metric learning to improve performance based on user input. For instance, Basu et al. [4] integrated metric learning and classification to assist users in refining clustering results. Their method adapts the distance metric based on user-provided constraints, improving cluster coherence. Okabe et al. [32] developed an interactive tool allowing users to adjust cluster assignments via multi-dimensional scaling and incremental distance metric learning, highlighting the value of interactive visualization in clustering tasks. Later, Okabe and Yamada [33] combined metric learning with constrained K-means. In particular, they proposed a boosted version of constrained K-means that incorporates weak cluster hypotheses and refines them using metric learning, an approach designed to be computationally efficient, while maintaining competitive performance with state-of-the-art interactive clustering methods.

Deep metric learning techniques. In addition to simple metric learning implementations, deep metric learning approaches have also been explored, with contrastive loss [12] being one of the most widely used loss functions for clustering refinement. For instance, Mitchell [30] introduced INCREMENT, a system that leverages user feedback to train a deep metric learning model. The model maps input features into a space where spatial distance inversely correlates with semantic similarity as determined by user feedback, using contrastive loss to dynamically adjust the learned representations. Similarly, Zhang et al. [42] proposed Supporting Clustering with Contrastive Learning, a framework that enhances separation in the representation space with contrastive learning, yielding significant improvements in clustering performance on short-text datasets.

In recent work, Wang et al. [38] proposed an interactive clustering method via metric learning to analyze energy consumption patterns. This approach allowed users to iteratively refine clustering outcomes by adjusting initial clusters and incorporating domain expertise. They showed that the proposed system effectively identifies distinct energy consumption patterns while outperforming traditional clustering methods, like K-Means [26] and DBSCAN [17].

Our contributions. Although several loss functions have been recently proposed in deep metric learning, they have not yet been examined in interactive clustering scenarios. Among the most popular are Triplet Loss [37], Quadruplet Loss [9], and ArcFace Loss [14]. This progress in metric learning has the potential to significantly advance interactive clustering and, consequently, all sectors where clustering is employed. Therefore, in this work, we evaluate these underexplored loss functions, along with contrastive loss, for interactive clustering across diverse, well-established datasets.

Moreover, although prior work has explored the joint use of clustering and topic modeling in interactive settings, supporting operations such as topic refinement, merging, and splitting [10], none of the aforementioned metric learning implementations integrate topic modeling into the pipeline. In our work, combining clustering with topic modeling in a metric learning setting facilitates more interpretable modifications by the user, since topic-level adjustments are typically more semantically meaningful and require substantially fewer edits than instance-level constraints. Based on this idea, we evaluate whether topic interactions can be effectively leveraged within a metric learning framework.

3 Interactive Clustering Framework

3.1 Interactive Clustering with Topic Modeling

Interactive clustering aims to refine clustering results based on user feedback. Given an initial clustering, direct re-assignment of data points (in our case, documents) into clusters can, however, be burdensome for users, as previously observed [13]. To address this, we integrate topic modeling with interactive clustering to create a more user-friendly workflow, where users re-assign topics rather than individual documents to clusters. This combination of topic modeling and interactive clustering has been shown to facilitate intuitive cluster refinement in prior traditional interactive systems, such as iVisClustering [22]. Our approach consists of six (6) steps as presented below (an illustrative overview of the overall pipeline which is divided in four main stages is also shown in Figure 1):

- (1) **Data Preprocessing (Stage A):** We apply lemmatization and stopwords removal on the input documents using the NLTK library [5].
- (2) **Text Embeddings (Stage A):** For document representation, we use BERT-based [15] sentence embeddings due to their strong semantic understanding and computational efficiency, specifically employing the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 model [36]; this model has been shown to produce more distinctive and human-interpretable clusters, as reported by Miller and Alexander [29].
- (3) **Clustering (Stage B):** For our experiments, we use both K-Means [26] and HDBSCAN [28], two of the most widely used clustering algorithms for grouping documents [7, 24, 31]. Due to their different operational characteristics (K-Means

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed interactive clustering pipeline.

requires the number of clusters to be predefined, while HDBSCAN automatically determines the number of clusters based on data density), using both algorithms allows for a better understanding of the impact of different deep learning metrics on overall clustering performance. More recent clustering methods, such as LLM-based approaches, could also be considered; however, they may obscure whether performance changes are due to the metrics themselves or the model-specific idiosyncrasies. K-Means and HDBSCAN, on the other hand, are widely studied, with well-known behaviors, strengths, and limitations, making it easier to interpret the effect of the deep learning metrics. Overall, the primary focus of this paper is to understand and assess the impact of different deep learning metrics on clustering outcomes, rather than to maximize clustering performance.

- (4) **Topic Modeling per Cluster (Stage B):** Once clusters are formed, we apply topic modeling to describe them. We experimented with Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) [6], a probabilistic model that represents documents as mixtures of topics and topics as distributions over words, as a baseline topic modeling method, and BERTopic [18], which leverages transformer-based embeddings and clustering to produce more coherent and context-aware topics, as an established state-of-the-art topic modeling method. Each cluster is assigned a topic represented by a distribution over words (terms) and we retain the top 10 terms per topic (hereafter referred to as *topic terms*) as a descriptive cluster representation. The “top” terms correspond to those with the highest probability or importance within the topic; by retaining 10 terms, we keep a balance between interpretability and sufficient coverage of the clusters’ main themes.
- (5) **User-Guided Refinement (Stage C):** The user examines the topic terms and their associated documents. If a term appears mis-clustered, the user can reassign it to another cluster, thereby moving also all its associated documents to the new cluster. For the purposes of this study, we do not rely on direct human interaction. Instead, user feedback is

simulated through an entropy-based oracle (Stage D) that mimics ideal user behavior based on ground-truth labels; the design and behavior of this simulated user are analyzed in detail in Section 3.3.

- (6) **Deep Metric Learning (Stage B):** Once refinements are applied, deep metric learning adapts the embedding space so that documents that should be together are closer, and those that should be separate are farther apart. The updated embeddings are then used to re-apply clustering and topic modeling, yielding an updated structure that aligns with user feedback. As illustrated in Figure 1, this process can support multiple iterations of refinement until the user is satisfied.

3.2 Metric Learning for Adaptation

A *metric* is a non-negative function that describes the notion of distance between two points in a given space. *Deep Metric learning* aims to learn such a distance function that reflects semantic similarity between data samples. Given a set of data points $X = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and their corresponding labels $Y = \{y_i\}_{i=1}^N$, the objective is to train a neural model that learns an embedding function:

$$f_\theta : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d,$$

parameterized by θ , which maps inputs into a latent representation space. A distance metric $d(\cdot, \cdot)$ is then defined over this embedding space, typically as:

$$d(x_1, x_2) = \mathcal{D}(f_\theta(x_1), f_\theta(x_2)),$$

where \mathcal{D} denotes a standard distance function. Specifically, for any two samples $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with labels $y_1, y_2 \in Y$, the learned metric $d(x_1, x_2)$ is expected to assign smaller distances to samples sharing the same label, and larger distances otherwise.

Once user refinements are performed, we use deep metric learning to adapt the representation space accordingly, so that the clustering algorithm is able to produce results similar to the requested adjustments. Specifically, we modify the document embeddings so that: (i) Documents that belong together (as determined by user

refinements) are brought closer in the embedding space; and (ii) Documents in separate clusters are pushed further apart.

A deep metric learning framework is then applied, where we optimize a loss function to update the embeddings. We then re-apply the clustering algorithm on the updated feature space, yielding a new clustering that better aligns with user preferences. This procedure is repeated for every iteration of the user feedback, until the user is satisfied with the final result. After carefully examining several loss functions, we selected the following four: the most commonly used ones (Contrastive and Triplet Loss), one extension of these (Quadruplet Loss), and one highly popular margin-based approach (ArcFace Loss). We describe each loss function below.

Contrastive Loss. Contrastive loss is the most used loss function in interactive clustering settings. It operates on document pairs $x_1, x_2 \in X$ and assigns to each pair a binary label that specifies whether the two documents should be considered similar or dissimilar. For a positive pair (i.e., documents from the same cluster), the loss creates a pulling force which contracts the space around documents that should be grouped together. For a negative pair (i.e., documents from different clusters), the loss activates only if the distance between the two points is smaller than the predefined margin. In this case, the embeddings are pushed apart until that margin is satisfied. Once the margin is reached, the loss becomes zero and no additional separation is encouraged.

Let the pairs $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with labels $y_1, y_2 \in Y$. Let l , a function equal to 1 if $y_1 = y_2$ and 0 otherwise.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{contrastive}} = \mathbb{1}_{y_1=y_2} \mathcal{D}_{f_\theta}^2(x_1, x_2) + \mathbb{1}_{y_1 \neq y_2} \max\left(0, \alpha - \mathcal{D}_{f_\theta}^2(x_1, x_2)\right).$$

where α is the margin. The first term pulls documents with matching labels closer together; while the second pushes documents with different labels apart.

Triplet Loss. Triplet loss is the most used loss function in the literature of metric learning; however, it has not yet been examined in interactive clustering. Triplet loss extends contrastive loss by introducing a third document into the training. Each triplet consists of an anchor, a positive example that belongs to the same cluster, and a negative example that does not. The central requirement of the loss is that the anchor should be closer to the positive than to the negative by at least a fixed margin. When this condition is violated, the loss increases and it encourages the anchor and positive to move closer, while simultaneously pushing the anchor and negative further apart. Over time, numerous triplets collectively shape the representation to produce tighter local neighborhoods in which semantically similar items cluster together and semantically different items are separated.

Triplet loss considers an anchor x_a , a positive sample x_p sharing the same label, and a negative sample x_n :

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{triplet}} = \max\left(0, \mathcal{D}_{f_\theta}^2(x_a, x_p) - \mathcal{D}_{f_\theta}^2(x_a, x_n) + \alpha\right)$$

where α is the margin.

Quadruplet Loss. Quadruplet loss builds on the principles of triplet loss and extends them by incorporating a second negative relationship into the objective. Instead of comparing an anchor, a positive, and a single negative, quadruplet loss introduces an additional negative pair that captures relationships between dissimilar clusters. It enforces two conditions: first, mirroring the triplet constraint, the

positive pair must be closer than the positive-negative pair by a margin; second, the positive pair must also be closer than the distance between two negatives drawn from different clusters. While triplet loss ensures that an anchor is relatively closer to positives than to negatives, it does not guarantee that negatives belonging to different clusters remain far apart from each other. Quadruplet loss explicitly forces these inter-class negative examples to be separated and creates a more globally structured embedding space.

Given (x_i, x_j) as a positive pair and (x_k, x_l) representing negative relations:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{quadruplet}} = & \sum_{i,j,k} \max\left(0, \mathcal{D}_{f_\theta}^2(x_i, x_j) - \mathcal{D}_{f_\theta}^2(x_i, x_k) + \alpha_1\right) \\ & + \sum_{i,j,k} \max\left(0, \mathcal{D}_{f_\theta}^2(x_i, x_j) - \mathcal{D}_{f_\theta}^2(x_k, x_l) + \alpha_2\right). \end{aligned}$$

ArcFace Loss. ArcFace loss takes a different approach, focusing on angular rather than Euclidean relationships. All document embeddings are normalized and projected onto a hypersphere, with each cluster represented by a vector on the hypersphere. The similarity between an embedding and its cluster is measured using the angle between them. ArcFace forces embeddings from the same cluster to become extremely compact while simultaneously pushing clusters apart in angular space. It modifies the classification objective by adding a fixed angular margin to the angle associated with the correct cluster before applying the softmax function and requires the model to reduce this angle to achieve correct classification.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{ArcFace}} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{\exp\{s \cos(\theta_{y_i, i} + m)\}}{\exp\{s \cos(\theta_{y_i, i} + m)\} + \sum_{j \neq y_i} \exp\{s \cos(\theta_{j, i})\}}.$$

Here, $\theta_{j, i}$ is the angle between embedding $f_\theta(x_i)$ and $f_\theta(x_j)$, m is the angular margin, and s is a scaling factor. The margin encourages tighter intra-class clusters and more separated inter-class boundaries on the unit hypersphere.

Below, we present the pseudocode of the proposed process:

- 1: **Input:** Document set X
- 2: **Output:** Refined document clustering C^*
- 3: **Initialize:** User satisfaction flag *Satisfied* \leftarrow **False**
- 4: **Preprocessing:**
- 5: **for all** documents $x \in X$ **do**
- 6: Apply lemmatization and remove stopwords
- 7: **end for**
- 8: **Initial Clustering:**
- 9: Perform clustering on X to obtain clusters C
- 10: **for all** clusters $c \in C$ **do**
- 11: Perform topic modeling on c
- 12: **end for**
- 13: **while not** *Satisfied* **do**
- 14: Provide to the user the clusters and the topic terms t
- 15: User refines the clusters by moving topic terms to other clusters; this results in the concurrent move of the documents associated with the selected topic terms to these clusters
- 16: Update document representations via deep metric learning
- 17: Re-cluster documents using the clustering algorithm
- 18: Perform topic modeling on the new clusters and update topic terms t
- 19: Update *Satisfied* based on user response

20: **end while**
21: **Return:** Final clustering C^*

3.3 Simulating User Behavior

Interactive clustering evaluations require extensive effort, while also being time consuming when relying on human involvement. To address this issue, we assess the effectiveness of our approach by simulating a user’s behavior based on *entropy-driven adjustments*, which are managed by a well-established method that imitates user interactions for semi-supervised interactive clustering [16].

We assume that the simulated user’s preferences regarding clustering results correspond to the ground-truth labels for each dataset and that the simulated user has full knowledge of these labels. Consequently, every modification to the clustering and topic modeling results is performed with the goal of mimicking the ground-truth labels. This allows us to construct an oracle approach to evaluate performance under optimal conditions, effectively testing its ability to reach the upper performance limit in each iteration.

Cluster entropy & labels. We first calculate the entropy of each cluster based on the known ground-truth labels of its documents. All clusters with entropy below a predefined threshold are then ranked in a ascending entropy order. Starting with the cluster having the lowest entropy, which means that it contains documents that mostly share the same label, the simulated user identifies the most frequent ground-truth label of the documents within the cluster and assigns it to the cluster. Each assigned ground-truth label is used only once. This process is iterated until all clusters under the predefined threshold have been given a label.

Topic term labels. Once the labeling is complete for the aforementioned clusters, the simulated user proceeds to analyze the topic terms. Based on the entropy of each term, again by looking at the documents belonging to this term, the simulated user assigns labels to individual terms. Here, different terms can be assigned to the same ground-truth label, as multiple terms can belong to the same ground-truth category.

Terms and documents reassignment. Having obtained labeled clusters and terms, the final step involves document re-assignment to other clusters. For each term, the simulated user determines the appropriate cluster and moves it there, which results in also moving its associated documents to that cluster. By iteratively adjusting clusters and terms based on entropy, the simulation imitates user-driven modifications, creating new data representations and clustering results, without requiring direct human intervention.

It is important to note that a single document can belong to multiple topic terms. In such cases, when the term is moved to a new cluster, all associated documents follow the movement according to the ascending order of terms’ entropy. Once a document has been moved as part of a term’s reassignment, it is effectively “locked” and does not follow subsequent movements triggered by other terms in that specific iteration.

The pseudocode of the whole process is presented below.

1: **Input:** Document embeddings X , initial clustering C , topic terms T , ground-truth labels Y , entropy threshold τ
2: **Output:** Refined document clustering C^*
3: **Compute cluster entropy:**

4: **for all** clusters $c \in C$ **do**
5: Compute entropy of c based on ground-truth labels of its documents
6: **end for**
7: Select clusters with entropy $< \tau$ and sort them in ascending entropy order
8: **Assign cluster labels:**
9: **for all** selected clusters c **do**
10: Assign c the most frequent ground-truth label among its documents
11: Mark the assigned label as used
12: **end for**
13: **Assign topic term labels:**
14: **for all** topic terms $t \in T$ in ascending entropy order **do**
15: Compute entropy of t based on associated documents
16: Assign t a ground-truth label (labels may be reused)
17: **end for**
18: **Reassign terms and documents:**
19: **for all** labeled terms t **do**
20: Move t to the cluster corresponding to its assigned label
21: Move all documents associated with t to the same cluster
22: Lock moved documents to prevent further reassignment
23: **end for**
24: **Return:** Refined clustering C^*

We also experimented with the Hungarian method [20] to directly map predicted clusters to ground-truth labels, instead of relying on entropy-based modifications. In this approach, a contingency matrix is first constructed between predicted clusters and true labels, and the Hungarian algorithm finds the optimal one-to-one assignment that maximizes the number of correctly matched documents. In our experiments, this alternative produced comparable results to the entropy-based oracle simulation. Ultimately, we chose the entropy-based approach as it provides a unified framework for handling both clusters and topic terms in the same manner.

4 Experiments and Results

4.1 Datasets

To evaluate the effectiveness of the loss functions, we conducted experiments on seven diverse datasets across different domains, document distributions, and text sizes (summarized in Table 1):

- **Tweet:** Comprised of 2,472 tweets split into 89 categories [41].
- **Search Snippets:** Contains 3,353 Web search transaction documents across eight domains: business, computers, health, education, culture, engineering, sports, and politics [35].
- **Darkweb:** Includes 3,461 HTML snapshots of websites hosted on the dark web organized into eight classes, such as financial crime, cybercrime, and violent crime [25].
- **Google News:** Includes titles and snippets of 11,109 news articles broken down to 152 categories [41].
- **Stack Overflow:** Consists of closed questions on Stack Overflow; we randomly selected 400 documents per category from the 35 categories with the most documents [40].

Table 1: Summary of datasets used in our experiments.

Dataset	# Documents	# Classes	Avg. Words
Tweet	2,472	89	8.56
Search Snippets	3,353	8	55.23
Dark Web Dataset	3,461	8	598.83
Google News	11,109	152	28.43
Stack Overflow	14,000	35	115.28
20 Newsgroups	18,846	20	160.29
AG News	20,000	4	31.06

- **20 Newsgroups:** Spanning 20 categories of 18,846 news documents. All classes have been utilized, with a document range from 628 to 999 per class [16].
- **AG News:** Contains 120,000 documents of 4 categories [43]. For computational efficiency, we randomly picked 5,000 documents per category.

4.2 Evaluation Methodology

Neural network architecture. The deep metric learning component uses a neural network with a single hidden layer of 128 units. During interactive clustering, the model is retrained for 10 epochs at each iteration. To assess the clustering performance, we also experimented with alternative architectures, with variety in the number of layers and hidden units. The tests were conducted using separate training and test splits for each dataset, in order to ensure that the network generalized well and did not overfit to the data. We selected the aforementioned architecture as it provided sufficient expressive power to capture the necessary patterns, while maintaining computational efficiency.

Entropy threshold determination. Prior to the main simulations, we conducted preliminary tests to determine an appropriate entropy threshold for our simulated user. Starting with a threshold of 0.95, as suggested by Dubey et al. [16], we then raised it to 1.0 before incrementally increasing it up to 5.0 with steps of 0.5. Our findings indicated that, for all datasets used, significant changes in clustering were observed when the entropy threshold was set to 2.0.

Loss function parameters. For all loss functions, we use the default parameters from the original papers: Contrastive loss margin = 1.0; Triplet loss margin = 0.2; Quadruplet loss first margin = 1.0 and second margin = 0.5; and ArcFace scale parameter = 64.0 and angular margin = 0.5.

Loss functions adjustments. To make Triplet loss and Quadruplet loss work to their full extent, we need to consider the selection of triplets and quadruplets, as not all triplets and quadruplets are relevant for training the model. Triplets can be classified into three categories based on the distance between the anchor, positive, and negative samples: (a) *Hard negatives* are the negative samples closest to the anchor. These samples are challenging for the model to distinguish and are the most informative for training. They require the model to learn more complex and discriminative features to differentiate between the anchor and the negative samples; (b) *Semi-hard* negatives are negative samples farther from the anchor than the positive sample but still have a positive loss. These samples are easier for the model to distinguish than hard negatives but are still useful for training; (c) *Easy negatives* are negative samples

farthest from the anchor. These samples are too easy for the model to distinguish and do not provide useful training information.

To maximize Triplet loss effectiveness, we employ triplet mining, a strategy that investigates possible triplets and selects the most informative ones. Triplet loss aims to pick informative triplets that contribute to successful learning by selecting “hard” triplets that are difficult for the model to correctly categorize and by avoiding “easy” triplets that the model can accurately classify. In our implementation, we selected triplets with the largest and smallest Euclidean distances between the anchor, positive, and negative samples, focusing on “hard” triplets.

A similar rationale applies to Quadruplet loss. A typical quadruplet consists of an anchor, a positive sample, a negative sample from a different class, and a second negative that is farther from the anchor than the first. The most informative quadruplets are those in which the first negative lies close to the anchor (hard or semi-hard), while the second negative enforces a stronger constraint by defining a clear ordering between inter-class distances. As with triplets, quadruplets composed only of easy negatives offer little learning signal, since the margin constraints are already satisfied. Consequently, effective quadruplet mining focuses on selecting hard or semi-hard negatives that violate, or nearly violate, the loss constraints, enabling the model to learn more discriminative embeddings that better align with user-driven clustering corrections.

Simulation procedure. We performed simulations with the four aforementioned loss functions (Section 3.2), iterating until the simulated user made no further changes or no improvements were observed in five consecutive iterations.

Evaluation setup and Metrics. For our implementation, we use PyTorch [34]. Experiments were run on two servers to parallelize processing: one with GeForce RTX 3080 GPU of 10GB memory and another with an RTX A6000 of 48GB memory.

To assess clustering performance, we used four widely used metrics. **Clustering Accuracy (ACC)** measures the proportion of correctly assigned samples under an optimal one-to-one mapping between predicted clusters and ground-truth labels. **F1-score (F1)** is the harmonic mean of precision and recall for cluster assignments. **Adjusted Rand Index (ARI)** quantifies the similarity between predicted and ground-truth clusterings. Finally, **Normalized Mutual Information (NMI)** measures the mutual dependence between predicted and true labels, normalized for differences in cluster counts.

4.3 Results

We divided the results by clustering method. For topic modeling, both LDA and BERTopic produced comparable outcomes, though BERTopic consistently achieved slightly better performance overall. For clarity and conciseness, next we report only BERTopic results.

4.3.1 Results with K-means. Since K-means requires a predefined number of clusters, we set it to match the ground-truth labels. This choice allows us to focus solely on incorrectly clustered samples and thus not limiting the algorithm’s upper performance bound, in line with prior work [38, 42].

Tweet (Figure 2a). This dataset is characterized by very short texts and many fine-grained categories relative to its size. The initial clustering achieved an ACC of 0.564, an F1-score of 0.633, an ARI

Figure 2: Clustering performance (Accuracy, F1, ARI, and NMI) using K-means and BERTopic.

of 0.458, and an NMI of 0.827. After the interactive refinement process, we observed substantial improvements across all metrics, with the Quadruplet loss resulting in the highest gains. In particular, Quadruplet loss reached a final ACC of 0.878, an F1-score of 0.879, an ARI of 0.939, and an NMI of 0.913. Contrastive loss and ArcFace

also improved steadily over the iterations but did not surpass the Quadruplet loss, while Triplet loss showed moderate improvements.

Search Snippets (Figure 2b). This dataset consists of a small number of medium texts and a small number of semantic categories. The initial clustering achieved an ACC of 0.595, an F1-score of 0.604, an ARI of 0.369, and an NMI of 0.471. After the interactive refinement

process, all loss functions exhibited some improvements, with ArcFace achieving the highest final metrics: ACC of 0.779, F1-score of 0.775, ARI of 0.569, and NMI of 0.551. Contrastive, Triplet and Quadruplet losses also improved across iterations, with Quadruplet loss reaching its peak using the lowest number of iterations, but remained below ArcFace in overall performance.

Darkweb (Figure 2c). This dataset contains a small number of long documents, distinguished in a small number of classes. The initial clustering achieved an ACC of 0.469, an F1-score of 0.580, an ARI of 0.241, and an NMI of 0.370. After the interactive refinement process, the Contrastive loss produced the highest gains, reaching a final ACC of 0.778, F1-score of 0.792, ARI of 0.557, and NMI of 0.464. The rest of the loss functions displayed similar results with Quadruplet loss and ArcFace converging early in the process, while Triplet loss used many iterations with very limited improvement over the last iterations. Triplet loss also showed some fluctuations occurring because of the scarcity of available informative triplets.

Google News (Figure 2d). This large-scale dataset has 152 fine-grained categories and moderately short documents. The initial clustering showed strong performance (ACC 0.690, F1 0.742, ARI 0.658, NMI 0.899). Unlike the other datasets, the Google News embeddings were already well structured from the outset, yielding smaller but meaningful fine-grained improvements after interactive refinement. Quadruplet and ArcFace produced strong improvements over the iterations, outperforming Triplet and Contrastive losses. Quadruplet loss achieved near-optimal results after just 2 iterations (ACC 0.856, F1 0.862, ARI 0.880, NMI 0.917), demonstrating remarkable efficiency. ArcFace also achieved high final metrics after 12 iterations (ACC 0.930, F1 0.864, ARI 0.826, NMI 0.930), but required many more iterations to reach its peak. The slight drop in NMI observed for Contrastive and Triplet losses can be attributed to their local, pairwise optimization objectives, which may over-refine already well-structured embeddings such as Google News.

Stack Overflow (Figure 2e). This dataset consists of relatively long, technical, and semantically similar documents distributed across a moderate number of classes. The initial clustering achieved ACC 0.430, F1 0.433, ARI 0.269, and NMI 0.443. ArcFace, Triplet, and Quadruplet losses improved over the iterations, while Contrastive failed to yield meaningful gains. Quadruplet achieved the best performance (ACC 0.447, F1 0.436, ARI 0.290, NMI 0.452), refining clusters with minimal user input (6 changes). ArcFace improved steadily but required more iterations to approach similar performance levels, while Triplet loss showcased similar results but with less iterations. The initial observed drop in F1 may be attributed to the high degree of topic overlap in the dataset, which leaves limited room for small, high-entropy adjustments. These early refinements can temporarily disrupt correct cluster assignments, leading to a decrease in F1; however, as subsequent iterations propagate the corrections, F1 recovers. This limited room also constrains the overall performance, as the potential for further improvements is restricted.

20 Newsgroups (Figure 2f). This is a large dataset with long documents and a relatively few broad categories. The initial clustering performance for 20 Newsgroups started at an ACC of 0.444, an F1 of 0.456, an ARI of 0.279, and an NMI of 0.442. By the end of the refinement process, Quadruplet loss achieved small but consistent improvements across all metrics, reaching a final ACC of 0.478, an

F1 of 0.479, an ARI of 0.307, and an NMI of 0.456. Contrastive and ArcFace also improved ACC and F1 but failed on improving ARI and NMI, while Triplet did not produce any meaningful improvements. In the early iterations, ARI and NMI temporarily decreased for all loss functions because local embedding adjustments improved individual sample assignments (ACC and F1) while slightly disrupting the global cluster structure. Quadruplet loss was the only one able to preserve inter-class ordering, leading to simultaneous improvements across both local and global clustering metrics.

AG News. For the AG News dataset, no term reassignments occurred during the interactive refinement process. Overall, AG News contains only four broad, high-level categories (i.e., World, Sports, Business, Sci/Tech), each represented by semantically coherent documents. Unlike high-class datasets, such as Tweet or Google News, AG News presents well-defined thematic boundaries and therefore distinctive vocabularies, making BERT embeddings and BERTopic particularly separable. As a result, the initial K-means clustering configuration is already highly stable, leaving no actionable inconsistencies for the system to correct (thus figure is omitted).

4.3.2 Results with HDBSCAN. It is important to note that HDBSCAN produces a variable number of clusters that may not match the number of ground-truth categories in the dataset. This makes traditional clustering metrics such as Accuracy and F1 potentially misleading, since they assume a one to one correspondence between predicted and true labels. Metrics like ARI and NMI are more appropriate in this setting, as they are designed to account for differences in cluster counts and are less sensitive to label permutations.

Tweet (Figure 3a). For the Tweet dataset using HDBSCAN, initial clustering performance across all loss functions was moderate (ACC 0.559, F1 0.571, ARI 0.174, NMI 0.647). Very few changes were detected during the interactive procedure, with only three user-driven adjustments identified. Despite limited feedback, all four loss functions managed to improve gradually, with ArcFace achieving the highest performance by the final iteration (ACC 0.743, F1 0.677, ARI 0.400, NMI 0.743). Contrastive, Quadruplet, and Triplet also showed improvements, though final scores were slightly lower.

Compared to K-means, HDBSCAN yields substantially lower final performance. While K-means benefits from a fixed number of clusters aligned with the 89 ground-truth categories, enabling fine-grained corrections and large performance gains under Quadruplet loss, HDBSCAN produces a much coarser clustering structure, reducing the number of detectable inconsistencies and limiting corrective supervision during interaction. As a result, although HDBSCAN can still benefit from metric learning, especially with ArcFace, its variable and reduced cluster count constrains the extent to which the embedding space can be refined, leading to smaller overall improvements than those observed with K-means.

Search Snippets (Figure 3b). For Search Snippets with HDBSCAN, initial clustering performance across all loss functions was very low (ACC 0.293, F1 0.169, ARI 0.012, NMI 0.036). Only a few user-driven adjustments occurred over the iterations, yet both Contrastive and ArcFace losses improved the embedding space. ArcFace outperformed the other methods, achieving its gains in fewer iterations and reaching a final ACC of 0.493, F1 of 0.531, ARI of 0.232, and

Figure 3: Clustering performance (Accuracy, F1, ARI, and NMI) using HDBSCAN and BERTopic.

NMI of 0.301. Contrastive followed closely but required more iterations, while Triplet and Quadruplet failed to benefit from the sparse feedback in this challenging scenario. The non-monotonic fluctuations in Contrastive loss stem from sparse user corrections causing local misalignments that temporarily decrease performance; subsequent iterations propagate corrections across the embedding space, realigning clusters and recovering the metrics.

Compared to K-means, the performance gap is substantial. With K-means, the fixed number of clusters aligned with the eight semantic categories allowed ArcFace to substantially improve all metrics. In contrast, HDBSCAN collapses the data into very few clusters at initialization, severely limiting the number of detectable inconsistencies and, consequently, the available interactive supervision.

Darkweb, Google News, Stack Overflow, 20 Newsgroups, AG News. For these datasets, HDBSCAN initially produced fewer clusters than the number of ground-truth categories, resulting in very coarse cluster structures. This high mismatch with the actual number of clusters can have several implications. For instance, ARI and NMI, although label-invariant, penalize excessive merging, and so even if metric learning slightly adjusts embeddings, the coarse cluster structure outweighs the improvements from refinements. Overall, the interactive refinement process identified only a limited number of corrective changes. This scarcity of feedback constrained the ability of all metric-learning losses to improve the embedding space meaningfully. As a result, most metrics remained largely unchanged throughout the iterations (hence, the corresponding figures are omitted). ACC and F1 showed minimal to no improvement, while ARI and NMI exhibited only slight variations.

4.3.3 Discussion. Table 2 summarizes each loss function behavior across dataset characteristics, from which practical guidelines can be drawn. Contrastive loss focuses on pairwise constraints without explicitly taking into account the global structure, performing well on small datasets (e.g. Tweet and Search Snippets), while excelling in datasets with long documents (e.g. Darkweb); its performance remains stable with increased number of classes, however, it scales less effectively to larger datasets. Triplet loss, while more expressive than Contrastive, is highly sensitive to triplet mining, therefore it

Table 2: Qualitative comparison of loss functions across varying dataset characteristics. Symbols indicate performance - ✓ : good, ● : moderate, ✗ : low, - : no impact.

Loss function	Small datasets	Large datasets	Short documents	Long documents	Many classes
Contrastive	✓	✗	●	✓	-
Triplet	●	●	●	✓	●
Quadruplet	●	✓	✓	●	✓
ArcFace	✓	✓	✓	●	✓

benefits from larger datasets where sufficient informative triplets can be mined, showing moderate performance. On small datasets, its performance remains average but it improves with increased data volume and document length (Darkweb, Stack Overflow, 20 Newsgroups). Quadruplet extends the triplet formulation by introducing a second negative sample, producing a hierarchy of distances and inducing a degree of global structure. It achieves strong performance on large datasets and those with many fine-grained classes, efficiently exploiting limited user feedback. However, its performance is moderate on smaller datasets and on datasets with longer documents. Both Triplet and Quadruplet are strongly dependent on the quality of the initial clustering; when initial cluster structure is poor (e.g. Search Snippets - HDBSCAN), the additional negative constraints tend to reinforce incorrect relations, leading to failure. ArcFace enforces angular margins on a normalized hypersphere, distributing all samples and modeling global class separation. This makes it the most structurally stable and effective across most datasets, particularly with HDBSCAN, robust under variable or coarse cluster structures. Only with longer documents its performance is comparatively moderate, and convergence can be slower.

Overall, for small datasets with long documents, Contrastive is suitable, while Quadruplet or ArcFace are more preferable for short documents. For larger datasets or many classes, Quadruplet and ArcFace are more effective. When cluster structures are coarse or variable, ArcFace is optimal, refining embeddings even under sparse feedback and cluster imbalance.

Computational Efficiency. The computational cost of the metric learning losses varies significantly, particularly on larger datasets. Contrastive loss, which evaluates all relevant pairs of samples, is the slowest due to the large number of pairwise distance computations. Quadruplet loss, which considers combinations of four samples, is slightly more efficient than Contrastive in our implementation, but remains computationally demanding. Triplet loss benefits from mining only informative triplets, making it faster than both Contrastive and Quadruplet, though still slower than ArcFace. ArcFace is by far the most efficient, as it leverages a global angular-margin formulation with minimal pairwise computations. While these differences are less pronounced on smaller datasets, the runtime ordering remains: Contrastive > Quadruplet > Triplet > ArcFace in terms of runtime.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

Here, we investigated the role of deep metric learning in interactive clustering by evaluating four loss functions, i.e., Contrastive, Triplet, Quadruplet, and ArcFace, across seven diverse datasets. Our experiments show that the effectiveness of each loss function depends strongly on dataset characteristics and the clustering method used. Quadruplet and ArcFace consistently improved clustering, with Quadruplet particularly effective on large, multi-class datasets, and ArcFace performing best under variable or coarse structures like HDBSCAN. Contrastive worked well on small, long-document datasets but scaled poorly. Triplet gave moderate gains, while local losses caused temporary metric fluctuations, and global losses like ArcFace stabilized embeddings more reliably. Importantly, this work highlighted the value of considering recent deep metric learning loss functions in the context of interactive clustering, an area that has not been explored by prior studies. Future work could enhance the framework by enabling dynamic creation of new clusters, allowing it to handle emerging or unseen categories, particularly in coarse or variable clusterings like HDBSCAN, while extending evaluation to even larger datasets and real-world interactive scenarios.

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